

Educational material

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Document elaborated by the WPs 5.1 & 5.2 of the FIN-CLARIAH consortium

DARIAH-FI

¹ In this new version, Jyväskylä University was replaced by the official name of the institution in English, which is University of Jyväskylä.

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1. Introduction

DARIAH-FI is the national research infrastructure for the digital humanities and computational social sciences in Finland. Developed jointly between the University of Helsinki, Aalto University, the University of Turku, Tampere University, University of Jyväskylä, the University of Eastern Finland, the National Library of Finland, the Language Bank of Finland, and the CSC – IT Center for Science, it provides tools, datasets, and workflows to support data-intensive social sciences and humanities research. More information about DARIAH-FI, its objectives and resources can be found on the website (<https://www.dariah.fi/>) of the information service.

To navigate DARIAH-FI and use its tools, datasets, and workflows effectively, this document first provides details about the state of digital humanities and computational social sciences education in Finland, as well as guidance (including educational materials, such as tutorials) on the different resources provided by the facility. Then, the document concludes by offering knowledge on plans related to digital humanities and computational social sciences training and DARIAH-FI, as well as information about where to find additional educational materials that could be relevant for using the research infrastructure.

2. State of digital humanities and computational social sciences education in Finland

2.1 University of Helsinki

2.1.1 Faculty of Arts

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
The approach is interdisciplinary and project-based, culminating every year with the Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon (https://www.helsinki.fi/en/digital-humanities/helsinki-digital-humanities-hackathon).	
Summary of the teaching offered can be found in the following link: https://www.helsinki.fi/en/digital-humanities/teaching	

Bachelor level studies	
Current teaching	<i>Introduction to Digital Humanities and Social Sciences</i> (https://sisu.helsinki.fi/student/courseunit/otm-a58814f7-ed13-43cd-b0b3-f01ea8fd383c/brochure), established in 2021 and iterated for the third time in 2023. Course organized both in Finnish and English.
Future teaching	Possibility to develop a BA track in English together with data scientists and scholars from closely related fields.

Master level studies	
Current teaching	<i>MA in Linguistic Diversity and Digital Humanities</i> (https://www.helsinki.fi/en/degree-programmes/linguistic-diversity-and-digital-humanities-masters-programme), established in 2021. The number of applicants increased to nearly 50 in 2023.
Future teaching	Possibility to design a couple more core courses together with scholars from closely related fields to further stabilize the MA.

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	<i>Digital Humanities Research Seminar</i> (https://www.helsinki.fi/en/digital-humanities/teaching/digital-humanities-research-seminar), established in 2015. Offered every year both in the autumn and the spring.
Future teaching	N/A

2.1.2 Faculty of Social Sciences

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
Teaching is offered through the Faculty of Social Sciences.	

Bachelor level studies

Current teaching	N/A
Future teaching	N/A

Master level studies	
Current teaching	<p><i>Master's Programme in Contemporary Societies</i> (https://www.helsinki.fi/en/degree-programmes/contemporary-societies-masters-programme). It includes extensive methodological social science quantitative method curriculum through the module <i>Research Skills</i> (https://studies.helsinki.fi/degree-structure/study-module/otm-57754ec4-f406-4cce-93fa-296658f350b9?cpId=hy-lv-74).</p> <p>Specific courses organized by other programs, such as <i>Network Analysis</i> (https://studies.helsinki.fi/courses/course-implementation/hy-opt-cur-2324-8b09deb5-fa84-4cd7-ab66-f5c9ecf46e85/DATA16001), organized by the <i>Master's Programme in Data Science</i>.</p>
Future teaching	N/A

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	<p>Specific courses organized by different doctoral schools, such as <i>Introduction to Open Data Science</i> (https://studies.helsinki.fi/courses/course-implementation/hy-opt-cur-2324-6bc9901d-e80d-4ba7-8bce-829e42c15521/PHD-302), organized by the Doctoral School in Humanities and Social Sciences.</p> <p>Some of the courses of the <i>MA in Contemporary Societies</i> can also be taken at the doctoral level.</p>
Future teaching	N/A

2.2 University of Turku

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
<p>Teaching is offered through the Faculty of Humanities, the Faculty of Social Sciences and the Faculty of Technology. Courses/modules are organized either as minor or major by the Department of Computing, both within linguistics, history and as a part of the data analytics track. Example of current courses/modules offered:</p> <p><i>Introduction to Digital Humanities</i> https://opas.peppi.utu.fi/en/course/HTDK0029/3955?period=2022-2024</p> <p><i>Digital Humanities for Literary Studies</i> https://opas.peppi.utu.fi/en/course/KOTK9715/20879?period=2022-2024</p>	

Bachelor level studies	
Current teaching	The courses/modules described above can be taken either as BA or MA.
Future teaching	N/A

Master level studies	
Current teaching	<p>NLP taught as part of the <i>Master's Degree Programme in Information and Communication Technology: Data Analytics</i> (https://www.utu.fi/en/study-at-utu/masters-degree-programme-in-information-and-communication-technology-data-analytics).</p> <p><i>Master's Degree in Digital Linguistics</i> (https://www.utu.fi/en/yliopisto/humanistinen-tiedekunta/digitaalinen-kielentutkimus) through the Language Specialist Degree Programme offered by the School of Languages and Translation Studies. Information about the master's thesis (https://opas.peppi.utu.fi/fi/opintojakso/DIKI1111/20151?period=2022-2024) and about the seminar (https://opas.peppi.utu.fi/fi/opintojakso/DIKI1011/20150?period=2022-2024).</p>
Future teaching	N/A

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	The Utuling Doctoral Programme (https://www.utu.fi/en/research/utugs/doctoral-programme-in-languages-and-translation-studies) offers a major in Digital language studies. The UTUGS also offers a major in NLP.
Future teaching	N/A

2.3 University of Jyväskylä

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
Teaching is offered through the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences.	

Bachelor level studies	
Current teaching	The Department of History & Ethnology offers an introductory course on <i>Digital Methods</i> .
Future teaching	N/A

Master level studies	
Current teaching	The Department of Social Sciences and Philosophy offers a course on <i>Data Collection Methods</i> (https://studyguide.jyu.fi/2023/en/courseunit/yfis3000/), where digital methods are discussed. Since Spring 2023: pilot course on <i>Digital Humanities Methods</i> .
Future teaching	N/A

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	Since Spring 2023: pilot course on <i>Digital Humanities Methods</i> .
Future teaching	Possibility of stabilizing the Digital Humanities Methods course with an overview of a variety of methods and tools.

2.4 University of Eastern Finland

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
Teaching is offered through the Philosophical Faculty.	

Bachelor level studies	
Current teaching	N/A
Future teaching	N/A

Master level studies	
Current teaching	<i>Master's Degree Programme in Linguistic Data Sciences</i> (https://www.uef.fi/en/degree-programme/masters-degree-programme-in-linguistic-data-sciences). More information about the contents of the master: https://opas.peppi.uef.fi/en/programme/118481?period=2023-2024 . <i>Digital Methods in Variationist Research</i> (https://opas.peppi.uef.fi/en/course/2119007/89483?period=2023-2024). The course is mostly for MA but can be taken also as BA.
Future teaching	N/A

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	N/A
Future teaching	N/A

2.5 University of Oulu

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
Teaching is offered through the Faculty of Humanities. It includes a minor program in <i>Digital Humanities</i> , which draws on expertise offered by a wide range of disciplines (e.g., history, information studies, language and linguistics).	

Bachelor level studies	
Current teaching	<p><i>Digital Humanities</i> (https://opas.peppi oulu.fi/en/programme/36890?period=2023-2024). Minor program within the Faculty of Humanities that includes courses on <i>Digital Research Methods</i> and <i>Digital Cultures</i>. This program can be taken either as BA or MA.</p> <p><i>Studies in Information Processing Science</i> (https://opas.peppi oulu.fi/en/programme/32017?period=2023-2024). Module offered within the <i>Information Studies</i> BA.</p> <p><i>Digital Humanities</i> (https://opas.peppi oulu.fi/en/course/682384A/6205?period=2023-2024). Course focused on methods for the collection, manipulation and analysis of digital data offered within the <i>English</i> BA.</p>
Future teaching	From 2024: new minor program in <i>Cultural Heritage</i> (https://opas.peppi oulu.fi/en/programme/36941?period=2023-2024), including a course on <i>Digitalisation of Cultural Heritage</i> (https://opas.peppi oulu.fi/en/course/HH00AJ11/32809?period=2023-2024).

Master level studies	
Current teaching	<p><i>Digital Humanities</i> (https://opas.peppi oulu.fi/en/programme/36890?period=2023-2024). Minor program within the Faculty of Humanities that includes courses on <i>Digital Research Methods</i> and <i>Digital Cultures</i>. This program can be taken either as BA or MA.</p>
Future teaching	N/A

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	N/A
Future teaching	N/A

2.6 CSC – IT Center for Science

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
Teaching structured through one course on how to use the Language Bank of Finland and its resources with the support of the CSC environment (https://ssl.eventilla.com/kielipankki). User support is also offered (e.g., weekly coffee).	
Summary of the training offered (webinars, courses, etc.) can be found in the following link: https://www.csc.fi/training#training-calendar	

Bachelor level studies	
Current teaching	N/A
Future teaching	N/A

Master level studies	
Current teaching	<p><i>Research Data Management</i> (https://ssl.eventilla.com/event/v8B6B). Self-study course that can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.</p> <p><i>CSC Computing Environment</i> (https://ssl.eventilla.com/csccompenselflearn). Self-study course that can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.</p> <p><i>Elements of Supercomputing</i> (https://edukamu.fi/elements-of-supercomputing). Course that can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.</p>
Future teaching	Possibility of developing a <i>Research Data Management</i> course specifically targeted for digital humanities and social sciences and humanities.

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	<p><i>Research Data Management</i> (https://ssl.eventilla.com/event/v8B6B). Self-study course that can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.</p> <p><i>CSC Computing Environment</i> (https://ssl.eventilla.com/csccompenselflearn). Self-study course that can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.</p> <p><i>Elements of Supercomputing</i> (https://edukamu.fi/elements-of-supercomputing). Course that can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.</p>
Future teaching	N/A

2.7 Language Bank of Finland

Scope of the training in digital humanities and computational social sciences	
Teaching offered through the Faculty of Arts of the University of Helsinki. It is structured through three open online courses related to different topics. Support in data management is also offered.	
Summary of the teaching offered can be found in the following link: https://www.kielipankki.fi/support/training/	

Bachelor level studies	
Current teaching	<i>Corpus Linguistics and Statistical Methods</i> (https://studies.helsinki.fi/courses/course-unit/otm-ee6245bb-57a8-4bf0-aae7-2bbf72dce531/KIK-404/Corpus_Linguistics_and_Statistical_Methods?cpId=hy-lv-74). Course offered twice a year both in Finnish and English.
Future teaching	N/A

Master level studies	
Current teaching	<i>Introduction to Speech Analysis</i> (https://studies.helsinki.fi/kurssit/opintojakso/otm-17e8fb4b-a951-4ad0-8773-d163131a31cd/KIK-LG212/Puheen_analyysin_perusteet). Course offered once a year both in Finnish and English. <i>Data Clinic</i> (https://studies.helsinki.fi/courses/course-unit/otm-ef0fec68-bc01-4e00-8da1-2c814b1d07e4/LDA-T309/Data_Clinic). Course offered once a year both in Finnish and English. The course can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.
Future teaching	N/A

Doctoral level studies	
Current teaching	<i>Data Clinic</i> (https://studies.helsinki.fi/courses/course-unit/otm-ef0fec68-bc01-4e00-8da1-2c814b1d07e4/LDA-T309/Data_Clinic). Course offered once a year both in Finnish and English. The course can be taken either as MA or at the doctoral level.
Future teaching	N/A

2.8 Others

2.8.1 Aalto University

No dedicated scheme to teaching digital humanities and computational social sciences.
Organization of a weekly informal get-together (*DH Pizza Seminar*) in partnership with the University of Helsinki: <https://www.aalto.fi/en/aalto-digi-platform/digital-humanities-in-aalto>.

2.8.2 Tampere University

No dedicated scheme to teaching digital humanities and computational social sciences.
Organization of some courses within the Faculty of Information Technology and Communication Sciences, such as *Digital Libraries and Open Science* (<https://www.tuni.fi/en/students-guide/curriculum/course-units/otm-d42bf3fb-eed7-43ee-919e-3a18e0b7d885?year=2023>) or *Statistical Methods for Text Data Analysis* (<https://www.tuni.fi/en/students-guide/curriculum/course-units/otm-e5b9699e-a176-44d8-8e64-790aa6320112?year=2023>).

3. DARIAH-FI resources

3.1 Ingestion

3.1.1 Data pipeline from NLF to CSC

This resource (<https://github.com/CSCfi/kielipankki-nlf-harvester>) allows to download copyright-free materials from the National Library of Finland through the CSC – IT Center for Science. Thanks to this resource, other providers will be able to easily deposit their data for research use in the CSC.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <https://github.com/CSCfi/kielipankki-nlf-harvester>

Resource developed by the National Library of Finland in partnership with the CSC – IT Center for Science, University of Helsinki and University of Turku. Collaborators: National Archives of Finland and University of Jyväskylä.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Johanna Lilja, National Library of Finland johanna.e.lilja@helsinki.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP3-1.pdf
Promotional video	N/A

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for	README file: https://github.com/CSCfi/kielipankki-nlf-harvester#readme

helping use the resource	<p>Description of the material in the Data Catalogue of the NLF: https://www.kiwi.fi/display/Datacatalog/Fin-Clariah+dataset+-+Copyright-free+Finnish+newspapers</p> <p>Documentation related to the metadata interface (DAM-API): https://wiki.helsinki.fi/display/Comhis/DAM-API</p>
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	<p>Guidance to NLF newspapers materials and METS/ALTO at the general level: https://github.com/NatLibFi/digitalia-notebook/</p> <p>General information about NLF APIs: https://wiki.helsinki.fi/display/Comhis/Interfaces+of+digi.kansalliskirjasto.fi</p>
Suggested courses	<p>Webinar at the introductory level on the use of the digi.kansalliskirjasto.fi service: https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/fi/uutiset/koulutusta-digikansalliskirjastofi-palvelun-kaytosta-21112023-klo-9</p> <p>Data clinics for universities that have joined the Tutkain agreement: https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/fi/palvelut/datapalvelut</p>
Other materials	<p>Pääkkönen, T. (2023). <i>The 20+ Years of Digitisation and Usage of Periodicals in National Library of Finland</i>. Available from https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe20231019140633</p>

3.1.2 Data pipeline from NARC to CSC

This resource (<https://huggingface.co/Kansallisarkisto/finbert-ner>) improves the usability of mass digitized state authority data in the National Archives of Finland through an AI based model for Named Entity Recognition. Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to better use the mass digitization service of the National Archives of Finland.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <https://huggingface.co/Kansallisarkisto/finbert-ner>

Resource developed by the University of Jyväskylä in partnership with the University of Helsinki and the CSC – IT Center for Science. Collaborators: National Archives of Finland, Tampere University and the University of Turku.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Jari Ojala, University of Jyväskylä jari.ojala@jyu.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP3-2.pdf
Promotional video	finbert

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	How to use guide: https://huggingface.co/Kansallisarkisto/finbert-ner#how-to-use Data sources used in model training, validation and testing: https://huggingface.co/Kansallisarkisto/finbert-ner#training-data
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	N/A
Suggested courses	N/A
Other materials	Poso, V., Välisalo, T., Toivanen, I., Holmila, A., & Ojala, J. (2023). Untapped data resources: applying NER for historical archival records of state authorities. <i>DHNB2023 Conference Proceedings</i> , 5(1), 55-69. https://doi.org/10.5617/dhnbpub.10650

3.1.3 Capturing game stream data

This resource (<https://collector-twitcher.rahtiapp.fi/>) collects chat data from the livestream service Twitch. Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to retrieve and analyze larger samples of chat data from the livestream service Twitch.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <https://collector-twitcher.rahtiapp.fi/>

Resource developed by the University of Jyväskylä in partnership with the University of Helsinki and the CSC – IT Center for Science. Collaborators: National Archives of Finland, Tampere University and the University of Turku.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Raine Koskimaa, University of Jyväskylä raine.koskimaa@jyu.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP3-4.pdf
Promotional video	Twitcher

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	Manual: https://collector-twitcher.rahtiapp.fi/Help About us: https://collector-twitcher.rahtiapp.fi/About_us
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	N/A
Suggested courses	N/A
Other materials	Koskimaa, R., Välisalo, T., & Lindroos, J. (2022). Understanding Twitch Esports Communities through Livestream Chat Analysis. <i>Book of Abstracts of the Esports Research Network Conference</i> , Jönköping, Sweden, November 21-23, 2022 (pp. 139-141). https://esportsresearch.net/wp-

	content/uploads/2023/01/ERNC22_Jonkoping_Book_of_Abstracts.pdf
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3.1.4 Recommender system for NLF data

This resource (<https://github.com/mrgransky/DARIAH-FI>) provides code for developing recommender systems to assist information retrieval in digital libraries based on log data gathered from their use. The resource is currently being tested on a dataset provided by the National Library of Finland (<https://digi.kansalliskirjasto.fi/etusivu>). Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to better analyze log data from other systems of the infrastructure.

Figure 4. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <https://github.com/mrgransky/DARIAH-FI>

Resource developed by Tampere University in partnership with the CSC – IT Center for Science and the University of Helsinki. Collaborators: National Library of Finland, University of Turku.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Sanna Kumpulainen, Tampere University

	sanna.kumpulainen@tuni.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP5-1-2.pdf
Promotional video	User based recommendation system

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	README file: https://github.com/mrgransky/DARIAH-FI/blob/main/README.md Documentation related to the log data dataset: https://wiki.helsinki.fi/display/DARIAH/WP3.1+Automated+Ingestion
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	N/A
Suggested courses	N/A
Other materials	N/A

3.2 Pre-processing and enrichment

3.2.1 Tool to evaluate biases & errors

This resource provides tools for subsetting (<https://github.com/hsci-r/octavo/>) and evaluating (<https://github.com/hsci-r/elasticsearch-openshift>) datasets that have not originally been created for research. Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to robustly explore large datasets, examine their representativeness, and extract the subset they are interested in.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the resource for subsetting datasets.

Source: <https://github.com/hsci-r/octavo/>

Resource developed by the University of Helsinki (ARTS) in partnership with the University of Helsinki (SOC), the University of Turku, the University of Eastern Finland and the CSC – IT Center for Science. Collaborators: National Library of Finland.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Eetu Mäkelä, University of Helsinki eetu.makela@helsinki.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP4-3.pdf
Promotional video	Subsetting and evaluating large datasets

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	<p>README file for the subsetting tool: https://github.com/hsci-r/octavo/blob/master/README.md</p> <p>README file for the evaluation tool: https://github.com/hsci-r/elasticsearch-openshift/blob/main/README.md</p> <p>Documentation and best practices for the evaluation tool: https://github.com/hsci-r/elasticsearch-openshift/tree/main/documentation</p>

Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	Additional resources for acquiring computational literacy for the humanities and social sciences: https://jiemakel.gitbook.io/cl4hss/where-to-continue
Suggested courses	<i>Computational literacy for the humanities and social sciences</i> . Eetu Mäkelä, University of Helsinki. Human Sciences – Computing Interaction (HSCI) research group: https://jiemakel.gitbook.io/cl4hss/
Other materials	N/A

3.2.2 Noise-resistant NLP

This resource provides resources for the multilingual modeling of web registers (<https://github.com/TurkuNLP/multilingual-register-labeling>) as well as a tool to classify toxic data in Finnish (e.g., insults, obscene language) from datasets retrieved from social media platforms (<https://github.com/TurkuNLP/toxicity-classifier>). Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able, for example, to detect toxic language use for Finnish.

Figure 6. Screenshot of the toxicity classifier.

Source: <https://github.com/TurkuNLP/toxicity-classifier>

Resource developed by the University of Turku in partnership with the CSC – IT Center for Science. Collaborators: University of Jyväskylä.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Veronika Laippala, University of Turku veronika.laippala@utu.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP1-3.pdf
Promotional video	How to make sense of web data?

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	README file: https://github.com/TurkuNLP/toxicity-classifier#readme Data used for the toxicity classifier: https://huggingface.co/datasets/TurkuNLP/jigsaw_toxicity_pred_fi

	<p>Model trained on the data used for the toxicity classifier: https://huggingface.co/TurkuNLP/bert-large-finnish-cased-toxicity</p> <p>Usage examples for the toxicity classifier, including a demo: https://github.com/TurkuNLP/toxicity-classifier/tree/main/prediction_scripts</p> <p>Concrete usage example for the toxicity classifier on a Suomi24 dataset: https://huggingface.co/datasets/TurkuNLP/Suomi24-toxicity-annotated</p> <p>Token classification for question-answer extraction for Finnish: https://huggingface.co/TurkuNLP/xlmr-qa-extraction-fi</p> <p>Token classification for question-answer extraction for English: https://huggingface.co/TurkuNLP/xlmr-qa-extraction-en</p> <p>Register Q&A: https://github.com/TurkuNLP/register-qa</p>
<p>Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Suggested courses</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Other materials</p>	<p>Laippala, V., Salmela, A., Rönniqvist, S., Aji, A. F., Chang, L., Dhifallah, A., Goulart, L., Kortelainen, H., Pàmies, M., Dutra, D. P., Skantsi, V., Sutawika, L., & Pyysalo, S. (2022). Towards better structured and less noisy Web data: Oscar with Register annotations. <i>Proceedings of the 8th Workshop on Noisy User-Generated Text</i>, Gyeongju, Republic of Korea, October 16, 2022 (pp. 215-221). https://aclanthology.org/2022.wnut-1.23/</p> <p>Eskelinen, A., Silvala, L., Ginter, F., Pyysalo, S., & Laippala, V. (2023). Toxicity Detection in Finnish Using Machine Translation. <i>Proceedings of the 24th Nordic Conference on Computational Linguistics</i>, Tórshavn, Faroe Islands, May 22-24, 2023 (pp. 685-697). https://aclanthology.org/2023.nodalida-1.68/</p>

3.2.3 Harmonizing Fennica metadata

This resource provides a harmonized version of the Fennica dataset (<http://fennica-fennica.rahtiapp.fi/>) as well as the code used (<https://github.com/fennicahub/fennica>) for cleaning, enriching and automatically generating reports on the data. Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to use and work with Fennica data for research purposes.

Harmonized Finnish National Bibliography

AUTHOR
Turku Data Science Group

PUBLISHED
Invalid Date

Preface chapter

As part of the Metadata Harmonization And Analysis work package, we use the Finnish national bibliography (FNB) Fennica dataset to create a harmonized dataset that can be used for research purposes as well as provide the groundwork for infrastructure that can be iterated further. The FNB contains metadata for 1,187,813 documents capturing records from as early as 1488 to more contemporary records.

Currently, the bookdown project comprises three distinct chapters. Notably, the harmonization process has been executed through the establishment of dual pipelines: **Whole FNB Pipeline** and **1809 to 1917 Period Pipeline**. These chapters are dedicated to the following metadata categories:

- Author's Lifetime:** This chapter focuses on the temporal dimension of authorship by capturing information regarding the lifespan of the authors associated with the documents contained within the dataset. This temporal context serves as a pivotal element for the historical and biographical analysis of the documents' creators.
- Author's Name:** Another integral facet of the dataset pertains to the recording of author names. Accurate identification and standardization of author names is of paramount significance for both bibliographic and scholarly purposes, as it enables the precise attribution of authorship.
- Publication Time:** The dataset also dedicates a chapter to the systematic cataloging of publication time, which is a pivotal component for chronologically situating the documents within a historical context.

It is imperative to underscore that this bookdown project is an evolving work-in-progress, and several additional fields will be incorporated into the dataset as they undergo the rigorous processes of data cleaning and harmonization. These augmentations will bolster the dataset's comprehensiveness, ensuring that it continues to serve as a robust foundation for scholarly research endeavors while maintaining high standards of data quality and integrity.

Figure 7. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <http://fennica-fennica.rahtiapp.fi/>

Resource developed by the University of Turku in partnership with the University of Helsinki.
Collaborators: National Library of Finland, University of Jyväskylä.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Leo Lahti, University of Turku leo.lahti@utu.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP4-1.pdf
Promotional video	Metadata harmonization

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	Repository, including a README file (https://github.com/fennicahub/fennica/blob/master/README.md) and examples on how to build reproducible data science workflows for digital humanities: https://github.com/fennicahub/fennica
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	N/A
Suggested courses	N/A
Other materials	<p>Lahti, L., Marjanen, J., Roivainen, H., Tolonen, M. (2019). Bibliographic Data Science and the History of the Book (c. 1500–1800). <i>Cataloging & Classification Quarterly</i>, 57(1), 5-23. https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2018.1543747</p> <p>Marjanen, J., Vaara, V., Kanner, A., Roivainen, H., Mäkelä, E., Lahti, L., Tolonen, M. (2019). A National Public Sphere? Analyzing the Language, Location, and Form of Newspapers in Finland, 1771–1917. <i>Journal of European Periodical Studies</i>, 4(1), 54-77. https://doi.org/10.21825/jeps.v4i1.10483</p>

3.3 Analysis

3.3.1 Easy-to-use interface for Nordic Twitter

This resource (<https://nts-csc.rahtiapp.fi/>) makes Twitter data available for researchers (from January 2015 to March 2023). Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to search, subset, visualize, and download user-generated social media data from the Nordic region.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <https://nts-csc.rahtiapp.fi/>

Resource developed by the University of Eastern Finland in partnership with Linnaeus University.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Mikko Laitinen, University of Eastern Finland mikko.laitinen@uef.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP4-4.pdf
Promotional video	Nordic Tweet Stream

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	Information about the NTS, including user guidance: https://nts-csc.rahtiapp.fi/about/ Statistics about the NTS: https://nts-csc.rahtiapp.fi/statistics/
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	N/A

Suggested courses	In planning.
Other materials	<p>Laitinen, M., Lundberg, J., Levin, M., & Martins, R. (2018). The Nordic Tweet Stream: A dynamic real-time monitor corpus of big and rich language data. <i>Proceedings of the Digital Humanities in the Nordic Countries 3rd Conference</i>, Helsinki, Finland, March 7-9, 2018 (pp. 349-362). https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2084/short10.pdf</p> <p>Laitinen, M., & Fatemi, M. (2022). Big and rich social networks in computational sociolinguistics. In P. Rautionaho, H. Parviainen, M. Kaunisto, & A. Nurmi (Eds.), <i>Social and Regional Variation in World Englishes</i> (pp. 166-190). Routledge.</p>

3.3.2 Tool for qualitative survey answers

This resource (<https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/>) provides a set of easy-to-use tools for conducting qualitative analysis on survey responses in Finnish. Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to better understand data retrieved from open-ended questions.

finnsurveytext 1.0.0 Reference Articles ▾ Changelog Search for

This repository contains an R package called finnsurveytext. For further details on how to use the package, please see the [package website](#) which contains tutorials covering all the functions available in finnsurveytext.

Installation

Install the released version of finnsurveytext from CRAN: `install.packages("finnsurveytext")`

Background

DARIAH-FI is one of two components of FIN-CLARIAH which is a research infrastructure project for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in Finland. DARIAH-FI involves all Finnish universities with research in SSH.

Our package, finnsurveytext, is the output of WP3.3 of DARIAH-FI. This is a joint work package with Tampere University, University of Eastern Finland, University of Jyväskylä and University of Helsinki with the objective of "better use of unstructured textual data in the context of Finnish surveys."

Motivation

Open-ended questions are an important but challenging way to obtain informative data in surveys. Open-ended question data usually requires extra time investment (Fielding et al., 2013), but open-ended questions are particularly useful if researchers do not want to constrain respondents' answers to pre-specified selections. Open-ended questions allow respondents to provide diverse answers based on their experience, and some answers are probably never thought of by researchers. (He & Schonlau, 2021.)

There's limited support for conductive qualitative analysis on Finnish open-ended survey responses and many researchers are more confident analysing responses to closed questions within surveys.

This package aims to provide a useful and user friendly set of tools for social science researchers to be able to analyse and understand responses to open-ended questions within their surveys.

Components

There are 5 sets of functions included in the finnsurveytext package. These are:

1. Preparation functions (R/01_prepare_conll-u.R)
 - These are functions to annotate survey data into a useful format (CoNLL-U) for analysis. There is a 'main' function within this set, `fst_prepare_conllu` which combines the other preparation functions and can be run as a single function to prepare data for analysis.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/>

Resource developed by the University of Helsinki in partnership with the CSC – IT Center for Science, University of Jyväskylä, and the University of Eastern Finland. Collaborators: University of Turku, Tampere University.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Krista Lagus, University of Helsinki krista.lagus@helsinki.fi

General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP3-3.pdf
Promotional video	finnsurveytext

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	<p>Tutorial 1: https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/articles/web_only/Tutorial1-Prepare_CoNLL-U.html</p> <p>Tutorial 2: https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/articles/web_only/Tutorial2-Data_exploration.html</p> <p>Tutorial 3: https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/articles/web_only/Tutorial3-Overview_of_Concept_Network_functions.html</p> <p>Tutorial 4: https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/articles/web_only/Tutorial4-Analysis_and_config_of_Concept_Network_functions.html</p> <p>Tutorial 5: https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/articles/web_only/Tutorial5-Demonstration_of_comparison_functions.html</p> <p>Tutorial 6: https://dariah-fi-survey-concept-network.github.io/finnsurveytext/articles/web_only/Tutorial6-Example_of_analysis_of_an_open-ended_survey_question.html</p> <p>Other materials: https://github.com/DARIAH-FI-Survey-Concept-Network/</p> <p>Demo: https://github.com/DARIAH-FI-Survey-Concept-Network/Concept-Network-Tool-demo</p>
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	<p>Fielding, J., Fielding, N., & Hughes, G. (2013). Opening up open-ended survey data using qualitative software. <i>Quality & Quantity</i>, 47(6), 3261–3276. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-012-9716-1</p> <p>He, Z., & Schonlau, M. (2021). Coding Text Answers to Open-ended Questions: Human Coders and Statistical Learning Algorithms Make Similar Mistakes. <i>Methods, Data, Analyses</i>, 15(1), Article 1. https://doi.org/10.12758/mda.2020.10</p>
Suggested courses	N/A
Other materials	Lagus, K., & Valaste, M. (2022). Qualitative survey data. Proceedings of the Baltic-Nordic-Ukrainian Workshop on Survey

	Statistics 2022, Tartu, Estonia, August 23-26, 2022 (p. 45). https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/publications/qualitative-survey-data
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3.3.3 LOD interface for parliamentary data

This resource (<https://github.com/SemanticComputing/sampo-ui>) provides a framework for building user interfaces for semantic portals. An example of a semantic portal created with this resource is the Parliamentisampo (<https://parlamenttisampo.fi/>). Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able to create highly customizable and responsive user interfaces without the necessity of having broad coding skills.

Figure 10. Screenshot of the resource.

Source: <https://github.com/SemanticComputing/sampo-ui>

Resource developed by Aalto University in partnership with the University of Turku and the University of Helsinki. Collaborators: University of Jyväskylä.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Eero Hyvönen, Aalto University eero.hyvonen@aalto.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP4-2.pdf
Promotional video	Parlamenttisampo

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	README file: https://github.com/SemanticComputing/sampo-ui#readme Tutorial: https://seco.cs.aalto.fi/tools/sampo-ui/Sampo-UI-tutorial.pdf Video: https://vimeo.com/817028609 Demo: https://sampo-ui.demo.seco.cs.aalto.fi/en/

	<p>Additional resources (publications, etc.): https://seco.cs.aalto.fi/tools/sampo-ui/</p> <p>General information: https://seco.cs.aalto.fi/projects/fin-clariah/</p>
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	N/A
Suggested courses	<p><i>Linked Data Technologies for Cultural Heritage and Digital Humanities: Introducing the Semantic Web in Video Lectures</i>. Eero Hyvönen, Aalto University and the University of Helsinki. Semantic Computing Research Group (SeCo) and Helsinki Centre for Digital Humanities (HELDIG): https://seco.cs.aalto.fi/teaching/sw-introduction/</p>
Other materials	<p>Hyvönen, E. How to create a national cross-domain ontology and linked data infrastructure and use it on the semantic web. <i>Semantic Web</i>, forthcoming.</p> <p>Hyvönen, E. (2023). Digital humanities on the Semantic Web: Sampo model and portal series. <i>Semantic Web</i>, 14(4), 729-744. https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-223034</p> <p>Hyvönen, E. (2023). Parlamenttisampo avaa eduskunnan miljoona puhetta ja kansanedustajien verkostot kaikkien tutkittaviksi. <i>Tieteessä tapahtuu</i>, 41(1), 36-41. https://journal.fi/tt/article/view/127064/76672</p> <p>Rantala, H., Ahola, A., Ikkala, E., & Hyvönen, E. (2023). How to create easily a data analytic semantic portal on top of a SPARQL endpoint: introducing the configurable Sampo-UI framework. <i>Proceedings of the 8th International Workshop on the Visualization and Interaction for Ontologies, Linked Data and Knowledge Graphs</i>, Athens, Greece, November 6, 2023 (pp. 28-39). https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3508/paper3.pdf</p> <p>Hyvönen, E. (2020). Using the Semantic Web in Digital Humanities: Shift from Data Publishing to Data-analysis and Serendipitous Knowledge Discovery. <i>Semantic Web</i>, 11(1), 187-193. https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-190386</p>

3.3.4 Tool for text network analysis

This resource provides tools based on network analysis for the analysis of political text. To that end, two tools were developed: KWIC tool for FinParl corpus (<http://finparl-01.utu.fi/apps/KWIC/>) and TNA tool for the analysis of speeches of Finnish MPs (<http://finparl-01.utu.fi/apps/TNA/>). Thanks to this resource, researchers will be able, for example, to analyze key word embeddings of the FinParl corpus (<http://finparl-01.utu.fi/apps/KWIC/>) and identify how phrases or longer text passages are re-used over time in the plenary debates of the Finnish parliament (<http://finparl-01.utu.fi/apps/TNA/>).

Figure 11. Screenshot of the KWIC tool.
Source: <http://finparl-01.utu.fi/apps/KWIC/>

Resource developed by the University of Turku in partnership with Aalto University.
Collaborators: University of Jyväskylä.

BASIC INFORMATION ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Leader	Kimmo Elo, University of Turku kimmo.elo@utu.fi
General information	Poster presented in the FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event (3.6.2022): https://www.kielipankki.fi/wp-content/uploads/Events/FIN-CLARIAH-2022-06-03/WP3-5.pdf
Promotional video	Text Network Analysis

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS ABOUT THE RESOURCE	
Materials (e.g., tutorials) created for helping use the resource	N/A
Relevant existing materials for helping use the resource	N/A

Suggested courses	N/A
Other materials	N/A

4. Future steps and other relevant information

4.1 Future steps

As described in section 2, the state of digital humanities and computational social sciences training in Finland is promising and evolving in the right direction, but there is still also a long way to go. For example, the range and scope of the training remains scattered between institutions, with some organizations more advanced than others (e.g., University of Helsinki). Likewise, there is a need for more staff dedicated exclusively to digital humanities and computational social sciences research and training (e.g., lecturers, tenure-track positions) as well as for more guidance about where to steer these fields. To that end, DARIAH-FI is currently discussing both the possibility of developing a national introductory course for the digital humanities and computational social sciences as well as the possibility of creating a national doctoral program for these fields.

4.2 Other relevant information

In addition to the information and guidance offered throughout this document, additional educational materials that could be relevant for using the research infrastructure can be found in the following links:

Methodological support offered by the Helsinki Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities	https://www.helsinki.fi/en/helsinki-institute-social-sciences-and-humanities/research-support/methodological-support
Training materials listed in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace	https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?categories=training-material
DARIAH-Campus	https://campus.dariah.eu/
Digital Humanities Course Registry	https://dhcr.clarin-dariah.eu/

5. Contact details

This document was elaborated by the WPs 5.1 & 5.2 of the FIN-CLARIAH consortium, affiliated with Tampere University (Sanna Kumpulainen, Anna Sendra Toset), in collaboration with the University of Helsinki (Haralds Matulis) and the national coordination of the DARIAH-FI research infrastructure (Risto Turunen).

For more information about this document, please contact the following people:

Sanna Kumpulainen	Associate Professor Faculty of Information Technology and Communication Sciences Tampere University sanna.kumpulainen@tuni.fi
Anna Sendra Toset	Project Manager Faculty of Information Technology and Communication Sciences Tampere University anna.sendratoset@tuni.fi

For more information about DARIAH-FI, please contact the following people:

Mikko Tolonen	Professor, PI for DARIAH-FI Department of Digital Humanities University of Helsinki mikko.tolonen@helsinki.fi
Risto Turunen	Postdoctoral Researcher, National Coordinator for DARIAH-FI Department of Digital Humanities University of Helsinki risto.turunen@helsinki.fi